

EXTRACTION OF MATRIX MECHANICAL PROPERTIES THROUGH IN-SITU NANOINDENTATION TESTING OF POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

The nanoindentation process on Drucker-Prager type materials has been modelled by FEM and the results compared to experimental results obtained in a range of polymer materials. The aim of the study is to assess the feasibility of this approach to obtain in-situ the mechanical properties of resins in polymer matrix composites.

Keywords: Micromechanics, Polymer matrix composites, nanoindentation, in-situ matrix testing, FEM

1. INTRODUCTION

The application of virtual testing techniques composite materials requires the use of multi-scale modeling approaches in order to predict the mechanical behavior of a composite from its constituents: matrix, fibers and interface. In the case of the matrix material, it is possible that its properties may be altered due the boundary constraints imposed by the fiber confinement, during both manufacturing and operation. In addition, for the prediction of the mechanical behavior of composite materials under hot-wet conditions, the hot-wet condition of each of the constituents must be characterized in-situ, because it is possible that the behavior inside the composite may differ from that encountered in the bulk. However, the in-situ mechanical characterization of the matrix in a composite material requires new experimental techniques, since conventional tests cannot be used in such conditions.

The instrumented nanoindentation method [1] is a unique micromechanical test that can be used for this purpose. In instrumented indentation, an indenter is used to produce a permanent imprint on the surface of a material, during which the load is measured continuously as a function of penetration of indenter. The hardness represents the mean pressure of indentation and although its physical meaning remains even now unclear, it

can be considered as a measure of the plastic properties of the material. In the case of pyramidal indenters, Tabor [2] showed that the mean pressure can be related to the yield stress of the material by a simple constraint factor in rigid perfectly plastic materials. Since then, the indentation of isotropic elasto-plastic materials has been widely investigated with the objective of determining the mechanical properties (Young's modulus E , yield stress Y and strain hardening exponent n) for nanoindentation tests. However, contrary to most metals, the deformation and the failure stress of polymers are greatly affected by the hydrostatic pressure, leading to an increase of the yield stress [3, 4]. A one-parameter yield criterion, such as Tresca and Von Mises, does not represent the polymeric behavior adequately since they cannot describe the dependency of the plastic behavior on the hydrostatic part of the stress tensor. Both, the Mohr-Coulomb and Drucker-Prager criteria, used for polymers, predict that the critical stress can occur in any plane and depends linearly on the normal stress in such plane. The locus of these criteria is either a pyramid or a cone respectively, which shows a good match with the experimental polymer behavior measured under pressure.

Several studies [5, 6] have shown that the pressure sensitivity has a marked influence on the indentation process, but this studies focus on spherical indentation and/or rigid plastic materials. The aim of this work is to carry out a thorough numerical study by Finite Element modeling of the process of sharp indentation in cohesive frictional elasto-plastic materials, with the final objective of extracting the mechanical properties of polymers from nanoindentation tests. For this, the process of conical indentation of a Drucker-Prager solid has been modeled. For practical reasons, two different conical indenters have been considered: 70.30° and 42.27° , since those have been found to be representative of pyramidal Berkovich and Cube-Corner indenters respectively, the two indenter geometries that are more commonly used in nanoindentation .

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

One of the first objectives of this study has been to explore whether some of the basic hypothesis that are usually made to analyze indentations in cohesive materials can be extended to frictional cohesive materials. In the following sections, the basic methods of determination of hardness and modulus by instrumented indentation and the physical meaning of hardness in cohesive elasto-plastic materials are briefly reviewed.

2.1. Determination of hardness and modulus.

Determining hardness and modulus from instrumented nanoindentation requires a method to estimate the contact area of indentation. The Oliver and Pharr method [7] is the most widely used and it relies on the estimation of the contact area from the stiffness of the unloading curve S (See figure 1).

However, the main limitation of the Oliver&Pharr method is that it does not take into account the pile-up/sink-in behavior of the material, as schematically represented in figure 2.

The pile-up can be defined by the parameter:

$$c = \frac{A_c}{A_{max}} \quad (1)$$

where A_c is the contact area and A_{max} is the apparent contact area at the maximum indentation depth (as measured from the initial height of the surface). Hence, when pile-up takes place, $c > 1$ and the Oliver and Pharr method underestimates the contact area, giving rise to errors as large as 50% on the estimated hardness.

Figure 1. Indentation load-displacement curve showing the most important parameters that define the curve.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram showing pile-up/sink-in effects affecting the contact area of indentation. These effects are not considered by the Oliver and Pharr method. From Taljat et al. [8]

To overcome this problem, Cheng and Cheng [9] found out that for cohesive materials, the ratio of the elastic stored energy W_{el}/W_{total} of indentation (measured from

the areas below the loading and unloading indentation curves, see figure 1), is proportional to the H/E ratio, which can be used together with the following equation:

$$\frac{H}{E^2} = \frac{4}{\pi} \frac{L_{\max}}{S^2} \quad (2)$$

to correct for pile-up/sink-in effects. The current study analyzes whether the observation of Cheng and Cheng can also be extended to cohesive frictional materials, in order to determine hardness and modulus from instrumented indentation in this type of materials.

2.2. Physical meaning of hardness.

It is generally observed in hardness testing that the mean contact pressure beneath an indenter is larger than the uniaxial compressive yield stress Y_c of the material. If yielding occurs due to shear, then the mean contact pressure undergone when the bulk is yielding in an indentation test, is higher than the stress required for a uniaxial compressive test because of the confining pressure generated by the surrounding elastically strained material in the indentation stress field. The ratio between the indentation mean contact pressure and the uniaxial compressive yield stress is called the constraint factor, C . For ductile metals, a value of $C \sim 2.5-3$ is generally considered to be appropriate [10], but this value is only valid when the indenter is in the fully plastic regime.

For elasto-plastic materials, Johnson [11] concluded that the constraint factor depends on the parameter $(Y/E) \cdot \tan\beta$, where β is the angle between the indenter face and the material surface. For small values, the indentation is in the fully plastic regime for which the constraint factor of 2.5 is valid. However, for larger values, the elastic deformation is no negligible anymore and the constraint factor decreases. For cohesive frictional materials, a few studies exist analyzing the constraint factor applied to spherical indentations [5] and pyramidal indentations [6], but the latter only considers very soft materials (small Y/E). The current study attempts to extent these observations to a wider range of materials (i.e. wider range of Y/E values).

3. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL DESCRIPTION.

Two-dimensional four node linear axisymmetric elements with complete integration have been used for the finite element simulations. The processes have been carried out using ABAQUS[®]/*Standard*. When the element distortion was unacceptably large, an adaptive remeshing strategy was followed using ABAQUS[®]/*Explicit* and in this case, elements with reduced integration and hour-glass control were employed.

Two different rigid conical indenters for the simulations: one, with a semi-apex angle θ of 70.30° and another with a semi-apex angle θ of 42.27° . This semi-apex angles were chosen so that the results can be considered as representative of indentation using two commonly use real pyramidal indenters: a Berkovich indenter, very blunt, and a Cube-Corner indenter, with a more acute angle. The chosen conical indenters have the same area to depth ratio than the corresponding pyramidal indenters. The specimen dimensions are large enough to neglect boundary effects and the mesh has been refined in the indented area as it can be seen in Figure 3. The mesh size in each case was

selected to maintain the same number of nodes in contact at maximum depth. In all cases, the contact between the indenter and the sample was assumed to be frictionless.

Figure 3. Finite Element Mesh employed to model a conical indenter according to a Berkovich tip.

To simulate the indented material, an elasto-plastic constitutive material model without hardening was employed, as representative of polymeric materials. The hydrostatic pressure dependency of plasticity can be modeled using either a Mohr-Coulomb or a Drucker-Prager yield criterion. In this case, the latter was used because the former involves numerical singularities leading to convergence problems when an implicit formulation is employed in the calculations.

In order to study the influence of the friction angle ϕ of the Drucker-Prager yield criterion as a function of Y_0/E , 30 different materials have been modeled with Y_0/E ranging from $5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ to 10^{-1} and friction angles ranging from 0° to 24° . The results were assumed to depend on the elastic modulus only through Y_0/E .

4. RESULTS.

4.1 Determination of hardness and modulus.

Figure 4 shows that the value of pile-up c is independent of the friction angle, and it only depends on the fraction of reversible stored energy during indentation. The Oliver and Pharr method only predicts accurately values of pile-up $c < 0.8$, indicating that the use of this method, for soft materials, may lead to errors as large as 30% on the estimation of the contact area of indentation. The values of pile-up obtained are in good agreement with those obtained by Cheng and Cheng [9] for non-frictional materials without strain hardening, and thus, this is a valid method to determine hardness and modulus in non-hardening frictional materials. This is important because in other types of materials, such as strain hardening materials, Alkorta et al [12] have demonstrated that the value of pile-up depends on the strain hardening exponent, invalidating the Cheng and Cheng approach for strain-hardening materials.

Figure 4. c pile-up parameter as a function of the reversible stored energy for three materials with different Drucker-Prager friction angles (the predicted pile-up value by the Oliver and Pharr method is included for comparison).

4.2. Effect of friction angle.

The friction angle has a large effect on the indentation curve, as shown in figure 5 with three indentation curves for materials having the same Y_c/E ratio, but different Drucker-Prager friction angles ranging from 0° to 24° .

Figure 5. Indentation load-displacement curves for three materials displaying identical Y_c and E , but different Drucker-Prager friction angles.

Figure 6 shows the hardness to yield stress ratio H/Y_c versus the ratio Y_c/E for materials with different friction angles when they are indented with a Berkovich indenter ($\theta=70.30^\circ$). The figure shows that for materials displaying a Y_c/E ratio larger than 0.1, the indentation is purely elastic and therefore, the hardness (understood as the mean pressure of indentation) is independent of the plastic properties. For Y_c/E values lower than 10^{-3} , the indentation is in the fully plastic regime and a constant constraint factor is achieved. For values of Y_c/E in between, the indentation is in the elasto-plastic regime and the pressure of indentation depends on both the elastic and plastic response.

Figure 6. H/Y_c constraint factor as a function of Y_c/E for materials with different Drucker-Prager friction angles ($\theta=70.3^\circ$)

More importantly, Figure 6 clearly shows that the constraint factor (H/Y_c ratio) increases considerably with the friction angle of the material, due to the effect of the hydrostatic pressure. This can also be noted in the equivalent stress contours of Figure 7, showing higher stress levels in the areas subjected to higher hydrostatic stresses.

The effect of the friction angle on the constraint factor is very large. For instance, for rigid-plastic materials ($Y_c/E < 10^{-3}$), the indentation contact pressure (hardness) changes from the well known rule-of-thumb value of $2.5Y_c$ for a non-frictional material (Von Mises type) to $4.2Y_c$, for a Drucker-Prager friction angle of 24° . Similar changes can also be found for smaller indenter apex angles ($\theta=42.27^\circ$), as shown in figure 8, although the constraint factors are somewhat smaller and the transition from the plastic to the elasto-plastic regime occurs for larger Y_c/E ratios. This occurs because the confining pressure generated by the surrounding material is more localized for smaller indenter apex angles.

Unfortunately, there is not a univocal correspondence between the indentation loading-unloading curve and the friction angle of the material since different combinations of Y_c and ϕ can give rise to the same indentation curve. Consequently, if one needs to extract the mechanical properties from an indentation test, it is necessary to gather additional independent information. In the following sections, two possible approaches are discussed.

4.2.1 Knowledge of Y_c

If one has access to additional information about the mechanical properties of the material, such as the compressive yield stress Y_c , then the friction angle can be extracted from a single indentation experiment using Figures 6 and 8, by calculating the constraint factor H/Y_c .

4.2.2. Dual indentation technique

Some authors have proposed extracting the friction angle by using a dual sharp indentation approach [6]. Based on figures 6 and 8 this should be possible as the constraint factor depends on both the indenter semi-apex angle and the friction angle.

Therefore, by computing the ratio between the hardnesses obtained with two sharp indenters (for instance, a Berkovich and a Cube-corner indenter) one should be able to compute the friction angle of the material. However, this must be done with great care since this is only possible when the indentations are in the fully plastic regime for both indenters, as shown in figure 9, i.e., at Y_c/E ratios below 0.002. For larger values, only the prior knowledge of Y_c allows measurement of the friction angle.

Figure 7. Von Mises stress contours with Berkovich indenter for (a) non-frictional material and (b) frictional material with Drucker-Prager angle of 24°

Figure 10 replots the values obtained in Figure 9 for a fully-plastic material ($Y_c/E < 2 \cdot 10^{-3}$). For the limit case ($\phi = 0^\circ$: Von Mises material), the hardness ratio is around 1.3 and it increases non-linearly in the interval $\phi \in [0^\circ, 30^\circ]$. This result differs from that obtained by Ganneau *et al.* [6] for the case of Mohr-Coulomb materials using yield design theorems.

Finally, it should be pointed out that all the results shown have been obtained assuming negligible friction between the indenter and the material. When friction is considered, a decrease in the Berkovich to Cube Corner hardness may be expected since friction affects the constraint factor more pronouncedly for smaller indenter apex angles [11]. Therefore, the friction coefficient between the indenter and the material should be taken into account for a precise comparison between hardnesses obtained with different indenters. This feature is in agreement with the experimental indentation results obtained in PMMA and PC, both materials having Y_c/E ratio below 0.03 [13].

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work attempts to extend the study of the indentation constraint factor C , to elastoplastic materials with Drucker-Prager pressure dependence in a Y_c/E range from $5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ to 10^{-1} and friction angles from 0° to 24° . For this purpose, different finite element simulations were carried out employing two different rigid conical indenters with semi-apex angles of $\theta=70.3^\circ$ and $\theta=42.27^\circ$ to obtain numerical data representative of Berkovich and Cube-Corner indenters respectively.

Figure 8. H/Y_c constraint factor as a function of Y_c/E for materials with different Drucker-Prager friction angles (Cube-corner indenter).

Figure 9. Hardness ratio (Berkovich over Cube Corner) as a function of Y_c/E for materials with different Drucker-Prager friction angles.

The frictional angle was found to have a large effect on the indentation process, increasing the load needed to achieve the same penetration as well as the constraint factor H/Y_c . Smaller apex-angles of the indenter produce smaller and more localized stress fields and consequently, the fully plastic regime extends to larger Y_c/E ratios with lower hardness values. However, no univocal correspondence has been found between indentation response and the frictional angle of the material.

The analysis shows that the frictional angle of the material can be computed, without prior knowledge of Y_c , using a dual indenter approach, provided that $Y_c/E < 2 \cdot 10^{-3}$. However, further calculations must be done in order to introduce friction between the indenter and material surfaces, to match the experimental results achieved in polymers.

Figure 10. Hardness ratio (Berkovich over Cube Corner) as a function Drucker-Prager friction angle for materials in the fully plastic regime ($Y_0/E < 2 \cdot 10^{-3}$)

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